

EARTH SCIENCES

POSSIBILITIES OF UNDERGROUND MAGNETIC EXPLORATION

İsgandarov E.,

Associate professor,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

Fetullayeva A.

Master student,

Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the question of the possibility of using underground magnetic prospecting for prospecting and exploration of mineral deposits, in particular, magnetized ore bodies. As is known, recently in the world practice of applying geophysical methods, digital instruments are widely used, which provide high accuracy of measured geophysical data. Underground magnetic prospecting covers magnetometric work in wells and mines and other underground structures and is usually carried out in conditions of approaching geological objects, which makes it possible to clarify the location of the sought-for minerals and, in particular, magnetized ore bodies.

Keywords: underground magnetic prospecting, borehole magnetic prospecting, magnetic anomaly, mine magnetic prospecting, vertical component of magnetic field intensity, full vector of magnetic field strength, magnetized ore body.

Introduction

In the search and exploration of mineral deposits and ore deposits, underground magnetic prospecting is increasingly being used. This includes borehole and mine magnetic prospecting. Magnetometric observations in mines are carried out to search for missed and deep-lying ore bodies, the anomalous effect of which on the day surface is insignificant. A number of works in world practice have been devoted to the issue of applying magnetometric work in underground conditions (Bergdahl, 1963; Afanasiev, 1969; Nikitsky and Glebovsky, 1990; Mochales and etc., 2008; Mukhametshin and etc., 2012; Beloglazova, 2014; Guo and etc. 2015; Xu and etc., 2019; Jianjun and Dandan, 2021; Kai and etc., 2021). In all these works, the results of the magnetometric work carried out in underground workings as well as in borehole conditions are presented. These results, as well as the studies performed on modeling magnetometric data, show the importance of underground magnetometric work.

The purpose of our research is to study magnetometric materials obtained in the field on certain areas in world practice (since such work has not yet been carried out in our country) and, based on the interpretation and processing of these materials in a modern interface, show the possibility and efficiency of carrying out magnetometric work in underground conditions.

Means and methods

It should be noted that field work carried out in underground conditions, including in wells, has its own specifics, but the measured values can be said to remain the same. As you know, when magnetometric work is performed on the surface of the earth, magnetic anomalies are ultimately calculated. A magnetic anomaly in magnetic exploration is the difference between the observed (measured) value of an element of the geomagnetic field and its normal value for a given area. Based on the results of field measurements, the following anomalies are calculated:

1. Anomaly of the full vector of magnetic field intensity (Logachev and Zakharov, 1979; Revyakin and etc., 1986) [8,13]:

$$\Delta T_a = T - T_n \quad (3)$$

Here T are the observed values of the total vector of the magnetic field strength; T_n is the normal value of the total vector of the magnetic field strength.

2. Anomaly of the vertical component of the full vector of the magnetic field strength:

$$\Delta Z_a = Z - Z_n \quad (4)$$

Where Z are the observed values of the vertical component of the magnetic field strength; Z_n is the normal value of the vertical component of the magnetic field strength. The anomaly of the horizontal component of the total magnetic field vector can also be calculated.

When calculating magnetic anomalies, it is necessary to introduce corrections into the observed values of the elements of the geomagnetic field. The main one is the correction for changes in the geomagnetic field over time. It is calculated on the basis of materials of continuous registration in time of elements of the geomagnetic field by special variational magnetic stations. With high-precision magnetic surveys, it may be necessary to introduce a correction for the excess of observation points relative to sea level.

In the case of borehole magnetic exploration, measurements are made along the borehole using a borehole magnetometer with a certain step of moving the device from top to bottom. In this case, the magnetic susceptibility of rocks χ along the well is measured, as well as the total magnetic field strength vector T_a and the vertical component of the total magnetic field strength vector Z_a , which make it possible to identify magnetically active geological ore bodies in the borehole environment. Let us consider the possibilities of borehole magnetic prospecting using the example of a model of a vertically magnetized ball with a radius of 1 km located at a distance of 2 km from the well at a depth

of 6 km. As is known, the vertical component of the magnetic field strength vector is calculated by the following formula (Lanza and Meloni, 2006; Serkerov, 1999; Tafeev and Sokolov, 1981) [7,11,14]:

$$Z = M \frac{2h^2 - x^2}{(x^2 + h^2)^{\frac{5}{2}}} \quad (1)$$

Where M is the magnetic moment of a vertically magnetized ball: $M = J \cdot V = 50 \cdot \frac{4}{3} \pi \cdot r^3 = 200$ gamm; x is the coordinate of the center of the magnetized ball along the x axis; V is the volume of the ball in m³ units; J - intensity of magnetization; r is the radius of the ball. Based on this formula, the Za values along the well were calculated on the computer (Fig. 1) and the

corresponding curve was plotted (Fig. 2). As can be seen, from the wellhead to a depth of 5 km, the Za values decrease from 60 gamm to zero, and then reaches its maximum negative value of -100 gamm opposite the ball center at a depth of 6 km. Then at a depth of 7 km, the Za curve reverses its sign and increases to a value of 60 gamm and then continuously decreases. Thus, it is possible to estimate the depth of occurrence of a magnetized geological body. The same picture is observed in the results of field observations along the wells crossing the magnetized bodies (Bergdahl, 1963; Afanasiev, 1969; Nikitsky and Glebovsky, 1990) [1-3].

Figure 1. Results of calculation by Excel.

Figure 2. Constructed curve Za from a magnetized sphere along the well.

In the case of underground magnetic prospecting carried out in mines or mine workings, observations are carried out along a straight line at a certain depth (Guo and etc., 2015; Jianjun and Dandan, 2021; Kai and etc., 2021; Mukhametshin, and Anisimov, 2012; Mochales and etc., 2008; Xu and etc., 2019) [4-6,9-10,15]. However, it should be noted that as the observation depth increases, the value of the magnetic field strength increases as the observation point approaches the geological ore body. In addition, measurements in mine workings provide additional material for interpretation, allowing more accurate determination of body parameters. Let us consider an example of interpretation of the curves of the vertical component of the magnetic field strength vector Z_a observed on two parallel profiles in a mine at different depths (Nikitsky and Glebovsky, 1990) [12], (Fig. 3). As can be seen, one observation line passes above the ore body (№ 1), and the second line passes below this body (№ 2). Both curves show Z_a maxima, which are shifted relative to each other in the horizontal direction, which may correspond to the inclined position of the ore magnetized

body. For a more visual representation of the desired ore body, a digital transformation of the Z_a values observed at various depths was performed. To do this, Z_a values were first taken at the characteristic points for each of the curves and the coordinates of the observation points were digitized in the "digid" mode of the SURFER graphic program and a "data" file was obtained (Table 1). Based on this file, a "grid" file was created, with the help of which a Z_a map was built along a section crossing a model magnetized ore deposit (Fig. 4). Then this map was compared with the original vertical section of the magnetized ore body passing through the observed profiles № 1 and № 2 (Fig. 5). As can be seen from the figure, this map more clearly reflects the shape and direction of the most magnetized ore body. However, it should be noted that when the observation profile approaches the observation line passing through the center of gravity of the ore body, the sign of the Z_a value changes to the opposite. But this does not apply to our case, when the observation profiles are located above and below the magnetized ore body (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3.

Values of the vertical component of the magnetic field vector Z_a observed on two profiles in the mine [12].

Table 1

Za values and coordinates of observation points

X, inc	Y, inc	Z _a , Gamm
0.564905761	126.3500949	-0.7
11.53216666	128.2574446	-0.8
24.40677729	125.39642	-1
35.37403819	126.3500949	-1.2
50.63283597	125.39642	-1
63.5074466	125.39642	0
75.90521979	127.7806072	2
90.68718014	124.9195826	3
106.4228153	125.8732575	2.9
121.2047757	125.8732575	2
137.8940858	125.39642	1.5
156.0139081	124.4427452	1
172.2263808	123.4890703	0.5
51.1096734	39.56568253	0
50.63283597	40.99619483	0
63.5074466	38.61200767	0.1
75.42838236	38.13517024	0.3
88.77983042	39.56568253	0.6
105.9459779	38.61200767	1
122.635288	38.13517024	1.5
139.3245981	38.13517024	2
156.0139081	37.65833281	2.5
171.2727059	37.18149538	3
187.0083411	36.22782052	3.2
201.313464	36.70465795	2
217.5259367	35.27414566	-1
229.9237099	35.27414566	-1.2
244.2288328	34.3204708	-1

Figure 4. Magnetic map along a section intersecting magnetized ore deposit.

Figure 5. Comparison of the Za map with a section of a magnetized ore body

Conclusion:

1. An analysis of the results of underground magnetometric work in mines and wells carried out in various regions and areas was carried out. Shown the possibility and efficiency of using underground magnetic

prospecting for delineation of ore bodies and other accumulations of mineral deposits.

2. A model magnetic field along the well for a vertically magnetized homogeneous geological body in the form of a ball was calculated and built on a computer.

It is shown that the Z_a curve changes its sign from positive to negative and reaches its maximum negative value opposite the center of gravity of the magnetized geological body.

3. Digital processing of the observed values of gravity was performed on the example of a model magnetized ore deposit. A map of the section of the vertical component of the full magnetization vector was built using a graphical editor in a modern interface, which more clearly shows the shape and direction of the desired magnetized ore body in comparison with the profile of mine magnetic observations.

4. Magnetic prospecting is an economically advantageous geophysical method and therefore it is recommended to use underground gravity prospecting in many areas, including in Azerbaijan.

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